

Transforming variability to profitability – variable seed rates in New Zealand maize

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Abstract

The use of variable rate seeding (VRS) in arable crops to match seeding rates to areas with homogenous paddock performance, known as Management Zones (MZ) is widespread worldwide. However, VRS has not been undertaken in commercial maize crops in New Zealand. This paper outlines a single maize VRS trial carried out in the 2015/16 growing season in the Waikato, New Zealand, to investigate the relationship between different seeding rates and MZ to maximise crop yield, but also gross margin (GM). This work shows that the use of MZ and VRS can provide a relatively simple, practical way of improving maize crop gross margin in a New Zealand paddock. Given the importance of farmers ensuring the minimisation of nutrient loss, we also believe that VRS is a valuable tool to minimise losses due to nutrient over-supply to poor performing zones in maize crops.

Background

Managing optimal fertiliser and seeding rates is one of the many challenges facing New Zealand maize growers. Currently, seeding and fertiliser rates are based on paddock historic yields from a number of years and crop expectations. This approach has significant flaws especially where spatial variability exists in the paddock.

Paddock spatial and temporal variability can have a significant effect on maize development, yield and profitability. Where within-paddock variation exists, precision agriculture has been found to be valuable irrespective of paddock size (Gemtos *et al.* 2005). Adoption of precision agriculture can minimise the impact of variability through efficient input management, resulting in cost reductions, minimisation of the environmental footprint and crop yield improvement (Reichardt and Jürgens 2008).

One aspect of precision agriculture involves defining homogenous regions of a paddock that possess similar yield limiting characteristics, and then applying similar fertilizer and/or seeding rates within distinct areas (Koch *et al.* 2004). These homogenous areas can be defined as management zones (MZ; Doerge, 1999). Management zones can have a specific rate of crop input applied using variable rate (VR) application equipment. Horbe *et al.* (2013), found that increasing the seeding rates in more fertile areas led to higher yields while low seeding rates performed better in low productivity areas. It is likely that this is due to the increased competition that may occur at higher populations. Shanahan *et al.* (2004) undertook studies with different seeding rates to investigate the relationship with low, medium and high performing zones in paddocks, concluding that VR Seeding (VRS) could be undertaken with MZ based on site characteristics such as elevation, electrical conductivity and soil brightness obtained from a simple aerial or satellite photo of the soil. There has been limited work generating MZ in maize crops in New Zealand, with Ekanayake *et al.*, 2015, using a combination of yield data, satellite imagery and farmer knowledge to determine MZ prior to undertaking a variable rate nitrogen trial. Even though within-paddock yield variation can be attributed to variation in soil chemical and physical properties, cropping history and soil type (Inman *et al.* 2005; Pierce and Nowak 1999; Sawyer 1994) MZ can be effectively determined using yield maps or knowledge from past performances experiences (Fleming *et al.* 2000; Hornung *et al.* 2006).

Precision farming has been undertaken in New Zealand since the 1990s, with limited commercial uptake. Most maize crops for silage or grain production are harvested with machines that have yield monitors installed that record GPS location, yield and other data every second they are in the paddock. This data can be analysed, and crop yield maps often show considerable variation between areas within a paddock. Managing this variability through the analysis of yield monitor data is used

widely internationally to apply variable rate nutrients, seeding rates, chemicals etc. to increase crop gross margin, and practical guides to carrying out the variable rate management are available (Jeschke et al, 2017). Modern maize precision planters are able to change their seeding rate on the go, based on prescription maps using GIS mapping programmes to define the population to be planted in different Management Zones (MZ) in the field, yet the facility is rarely utilised. Some of the anecdotal evidence for slow uptake is due to lack of data or know how to generate precision maps required to create MZ. Empirical evidence to prove the financial benefits of the use of VRS in New Zealand maize crops is also non-existent.

The aims of this work were to:

1. Use existing yield maps to determine within-paddock maize yield variability
2. Generate different MZ
3. Identify the highest yielding and most profitable seeding rates across a range of paddock MZ

By planting using VRS targeting different MZ, we are effectively targeting different yields in each MZ.

Methods

A long-term maize paddock (20+ years in maize) with historical yield map data was selected in the Waikato Region. The soil type was a poorly drained Puniu gley soil. The paddock was considered to possess sufficient spatial variability to allow for within paddock measurable yield differences, with a gentle slope from rolling hill country to a low-lying alluvial site. Thirty-year weather average records are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Average weather data from 1981-2010 for NIWA Waikeria 2 weather station for growing season (8km from trial site)

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Oct	Nov	Dec	Annual
Total Rainfall (mm)	74.1	68.9	78.2	101.6	82.1	92.5	1114.9
Mean Air Temperature (°C)	18.4	18.9	16.8	13	14.9	17.1	13.6
Mean Daily Maximum Air Temperature (°C)	24.6	25	23.2	18.1	20.3	22.6	19.2
Mean Daily Minimum Air Temperature (°C)	12.3	12.8	10.5	7.9	9.5	11.6	8.1

Six years of data files from harvester yield monitors (2008 – 2011 and 2014 – 2015) were obtained for the paddock and analysed for spatial and temporal variability. The multi-year data were normalised and then aggregated to create three management zones (MZ): High yield Stable (HS); Low yield Stable (LS) and unstable (US). Normalized yield is the ratio of the actual yield at a specific point to the paddock average. On that basis, the normalised yields for the three management zones and their respective areas are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Average normalised yield and CVs in three management zones

	Unstable	Low Stable	High Stable
Normalised yield (%)	84.8	9	114.3
CV (%)	38.1	24.2	19.5
Area (Ha)	0.9	2.9	8.2

Stable zones were defined as having less than 30% coefficient of variance over the six years, while those where the coefficient was greater than 30% were considered unstable. Areas with a normalised yield higher than 100% were defined as high yielding and those with less than 100% of normalised yield were low yielding. These MZ are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Zone management map (U=Unstable; LS=Low Stable & HS=High Stable)

In spring 2016, a seeding rate experiment was established in part of the paddock to investigate the effect of four seeding rates (75, 90, 105 and 120 thousand seeds/ha) across the three management zones. The experiment was a completely randomised block design replicated four times.

Plots were eight rows wide (76.2cm row spacing) by approximately 180 metres long. Pioneer® hybrid P0791 (106 CRM) was planted on 5 October 2015. Starter fertiliser was applied as grower best practice, and the maize was side dressed at approximately V4 stage as grower standard practice.

Established plant counts were determined at maize growth stage V6, across the MZ. The maize grain crop was harvested using a John Deere combine harvester with yield monitor on 21 May 2016.

Gross Margin was calculated using the costs and returns given in Table 3 below. No value for the land was included.

Table 3. Values used to calculate crop gross margin

	Expenditure	Income
Fixed costs	\$1440 per hectare	
Grain cartage	\$18 per wet tonne	
Grain drying	\$24 per wet tonne + \$2 per % moisture above 20%	
Maize seed	\$6 per 1,000 seeds	
Grain (@14% moisture)		\$450 per tonne

Results & discussion

The average maize grain yield was 13.3 t/ha, with yields at different locations within the paddock ranging from less than 8 t/ha to greater than 18 t/ha, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Maize grain yield in the trial paddock in 2016 (t/ha @ 14% DM)

Zone analysis:

Data from the harvester yield monitor was obtained after the paddock harvest, and was analysed according to Management Zone. The yield is shown in Figure 3 Yield by seeding rate and Management Zone and gross margin (GM) was calculated and are shown in Table 4 and Figure 4.

Table 4. Gross Margin generated from different zones and seed rates (\$/ha). Bold value show highest GM for each MZ

Yield Zone	Planting rate ('000's / hectare)				Average	CV
	75	90	105	120		
Unstable	n/a	\$2,033	n/a	\$1,251	\$1,251	20.7%
Low Stable	\$2,339	\$2,043	\$2,148	\$1,913	\$2,105	15.8%
High Stable	\$2,584	\$2,704	\$2,850	\$2,160	\$2,570	16.7%
Average	\$2,522	\$2,504	\$2,680	\$2,007	n/a	17.4%
CV	17.7%	16.9%	14.0%	18.9%	17.4%	-

The seeding rate that returned the highest GM in the Low Stable zone was 75,000 seeds/hectare; 105,000 s/ha in the High Stable zone, and 90,000 s/ha in the Unstable zone.

Based on these results, the effect of planting the entire paddock using VRS was calculated. If the entire paddock were planted at 90,000 seeds per hectare, as would be the commercial norm, the total paddock GM would be \$30,048. If planted using Variable Rate Seeding, the paddock GM would be \$31,983, an increase of \$161 per hectare over the constant seed rate. Horbe *et al.* (2013), found a similar result, with the net economic effect of VRS application being a US\$113-342/ha increase in margin.

Regression analysis

Based on the regression analysis relationship line for the HS MZ shown in Figure 3 below, grain yield per hectare, and consequently total gross income per hectare, was maximised when planted at 94,600 seeds/ha. For the LS MZ maximum yield was obtained at 94,200 seed/ha. The relationship between seeding rate and yield for the HS MZ is typical of seeding rate and yield population relationships (Duncan, 1984). However, our finding that the seeding rate in the LS and HS MZ resulting in highest yield are essentially the same contradicts findings of other research showing greater yield response to seeding density in higher yielding areas compared to low yielding areas (Horbe *et al.* 2013; Shanahan, 2004)

The HS MZ yielded significantly higher than the LS MZ did in three of the four seeding rates (LSD=0.1), but not at the seeding rate of 75,000 per hectare.

Figure 3. Yield by seeding rate and Management Zone

However, taking account of the price of maize seed, the highest Gross Margin per hectare is obtained at a seeding rate lower than the rate that achieves the highest yield per hectare, as shown in Figure 4 below.

For the HS MZ the optimal seeding rate to maximise GM was 92,500 seeds per hectare, several thousand lower than the seeding rate that achieved the highest yield.

For the LS MZ, it is not possible to calculate the optimal seeding rate for maximising GM, because the results suggest the seeding rate that will result in the highest GM is lower than the 75,000 per hectare planted in the trial. There was insufficient data from the Unstable MZ to undertake further analysis.

Figure 4. Gross Margin by seeding rate and MZ

By planting using VRS targeting different MZ, we are effectively targeting different yields in each MZ. Currently the same rate of fertiliser is applied to each MZ, despite the different yield targets. Tremblay *et al.*, (2007), found that the optimal rate of nitrogen fertiliser for different zones within the same paddock in Quebec ranged from less than 50 kg/ha to more than 200 kg/ha. It is practically feasible to target crop nutrients, and other inputs, to the different MZ, leading to more nutrients being available in the High Stable MZ, and less nutrients applied to the Low Stable MZ, reducing the risk of nutrient loss. It is necessary to undertake further work optimising the seeding rate to MZ in different conditions, as the relationship of yield to seed rate will vary, as claimed by Licht *et al.*, (2016); and Woli *et al.*, (2014).

Conclusion

It is important to consider that this work is based on a single trial, in one season, and results will vary between sites and seasons, and between maize grain and silage crops. The optimal seeding rates to maximise Gross Margin will vary based on the value of maize grain and silage, and the price of maize seed.

This work shows that the use of MZ and VRS can provide a relatively simple, practical way of improving maize crop gross margin in a New Zealand paddock. It is necessary to undertake further work optimising the seeding rate to MZ in different conditions, as the relationship of yield to seed rate will vary. To this end, in the 2016 planting season FAR established another three trials to support the implementation and validation of the use of VRS in other maize crops in the North Island.

Given the importance of farmers ensuring the minimisation of nutrient loss, we also believe that VRS is a valuable tool to minimise losses of nutrients because of over-supply to poor performing zones in maize crops.

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